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New records of *Aphidius eglanteriae* Haliday, 1834 (Hymenoptera, Braconidae, Aphidiinae) from Western Europe

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Kaliuzhna, M.O. & van Achterberg, C. New records of *Aphidius eglanteriae* Haliday, 1834 (Hymenoptera, Braconidae, Aphidiinae) from western Europe. — The first record of *Aphidius eglanteriae* from The Netherlands and new records from France are presented. Information on distribution and notes on morphology of the species is given. High resolution microphotographs of *A. eglanteriae* are provided.

Key words: Braconidae, Aphidiinae, The Netherlands, first record, France, new records, distribution.

Калюжна, М.О. і ван Ахтерберг, К. Нові знахідки *Aphidius eglanteriae* Haliday, 1834 (Hymenoptera, Braconidae, Aphidiinae) із Західної Європи. — У статті наведено першу знахідку *Aphidius eglanteriae* з Нідерландів і нові знахідки із Франції. Дано інформацію про поширення та нотатки щодо морфології виду. Стаття проілюстрована мікрофотографіями *A. eglanteriae* у високій роздільній здатності.

Ключові слова: Braconidae, Aphidiinae, Нідерланди, перша знахідка, Франція, нові знахідки, поширення.

Introduction

Aphidius eglanteriae Haliday, 1834 belongs to the subfamily Aphidiinae (Hymenoptera, Braconidae), which are specialized koinobiont endoparasitoids of aphids. This species is known from Western Palaearctic Region (including western Himalaya of northern India: Das & Chakrabarti, 1990; Yu *et al.*, 2016). In western Europe *A. eglanteriae* is known from France (mainland), Germany, and United Kingdom (Starý, 1971, 1973, Yu *et al.*, 2016). In addition, this species is listed for The Netherlands in the on-line databases of Fauna Europaea (2019) and Naturalis Biodiversity Center (Creuwels & Pieterse, 2019) by one of the authors, C. van Achterberg, on the basis of unpublished material what is listed in this paper. In addition, material that has been received for the identification this year by the first author revealed to be new for the fauna of the departments Lot-et-Garonne and Dordogne in France. Here we present these new records of *A. eglanteriae*, to facilitate knowledge on the distribution of this species together with some notes on the morphology.

Material and Methods

The material from The Netherlands is deposited in the Naturalis Biodiversity Center (RMNH), Leiden, The Netherlands. The original photographs of these specimens were taken using Zeiss Stereo Discovery V.12 Microscope and Zeiss AxioCam MRc5 with AxioVision SE64 Rel. 4.9.1. software. The label scans were taken with a Canon CanoScan 9000F. The material from France is deposited in I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (SIZK), Kyiv, Ukraine. The original photographs were taken using a Leica Z16 APO stereomicroscope equipped with a Leica DFC 450 camera and processed with LAS V3.8 software. Some images were processed using GIMP 2.8. Geographical coordinates were found using Google Earth Pro 7.3.2.5776 (64-bit). They show not exact location of specimen collection point but the location of the city mentioned on the label.

***Aphidius eglanteriae* Haliday, 1834 (figs 1–11)**

Material. The Netherlands (figs 1–4), Wageningen, 51°59'06.74" N, 5°39'56.12" E: 26.06.1972, 1 ♀, leg. H. H. Evenhuis, mummy between flower buds of *Rosa rugosa*, det. H. H. Evenhuis, 1975 (RMNH. INS. 1264302); IPO-ground, 13.06.1975, 1 ♀, leg. H. H. Evenhuis, mummy on cultivated rose, det. H. H. Evenhuis, 1976 (RMNH. INS. 1264303); idem, 1 ♀ (RMNH. INS. 1264305); 1 ♀, 13.06.1975, leg. H. H. Evenhuis, mummy on cultivated *Rosa* sp., det. H. H. Evenhuis, 1976 (RMNH. INS. 1264304). The aphid host species for the examined specimens of *A. eglanteriae* from The Netherlands are not known. **France (figs 5–11):** reared from *Chaetosiphon* sp. collected on commercial strawberry in different companies at three locations: 11.03.2019, Villeneuve-sur-Lot (Lot-et-Garonne, Aquitaine), 44°24'28.34" N, 0°42'25.98" E; 11.03.2019, Cendrieux (Dordogne, Aquitaine), 44°59'43.92" N, 0°49'22.86" E; 25.04.2019, Sainte-Livrade-sur-Lot (Lot-et-Garonne, Aquitaine), 44°23'51.89" N, 0°35'16.82" E, 22 ♀, 22 ♂, leg. C. Phillip (SIZK).

General distribution. Czech Republic (Yu *et al.*, 2012), France (mainland) (Starý *et al.*, 1971, 1973, Yu *et al.*, 2012) Germany, Hungary, India (Uttar Pradesh), Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Moldova, Montenegro, Netherlands (**new record**), Poland (Yu *et al.*, 2016), Russia (St. Petersburg, Krasnodar Territory and Novosibirsk Province) (Davidian, 2018), Serbia, Turkey, United Kingdom (Yu *et al.*, 2016). For now, *A. eglanteriae* is unknown from Ukraine; however, its occurrence is likely because it occurs in adjacent countries.

Distribution in France. Moulinet, Col De Turini (Alpes-Maritimes), Peyrus (Drôme), Le Fayet (Hte-Savoie), La Grave, Nevache et Vars (Hautes-Aples) (Starý

et al., 1971; Starý, 1973), Nord, Sarthe, Rhône (Rabasse *et al.*, 2001), Villeneuve-sur-Lot and Sainte-Livrade-sur-Lot (Lot-et-Garonne, Aquitaine) (new record), Cendrieux (Dordogne, Aquitaine) (new record).

Hosts. *Capitophorus formosartemisiae* on *Artemisia* sp.; *Chaetosiphon* spp. (*C. alpestre*, *C. chaetosiphon*, *C. fragaefolii*, *C. tetraerhodum*) mostly on *Rosa* spp. (Yu *et al.*, 2016) and *C. fragaefolii* on commercial strawberry (Rabasse *et al.*, 2001; Yu *et al.*, 2016); *Longicaudus trirhodus* on *Rosa* spp. and *Thalictrum* spp.; *Macrosiphoniella pseudoartemisiae* on *Artemisia vulgaris*; *Myzaphis rosarum* on *Rosa webbiana*; *Myzus sorbi* on *Sorbaria tomentosa* (Yu *et al.*, 2016).

Notes on morphology

Female: 13–14 (15)-segmented antenna (14–15 according Haliday, 1834); tentorial index 0.3; ocellar triangle right; temples as long as eyes (in dorsal view); maxillary palp 4- and labial palp 2-segmented; F1 (= third antennal segment) as long as F2 and 3.3–4.0 times as long as wide (and F2 slightly wider than F1); first metasomal tergite 3.0–3.4 times longer than wide at level of spiracles; anterolateral area of the first metasomal tergite has 5–6 (7) costulae that is less than 9–12 mentioned by Starý (1973);

Figs 1–4. *Aphidius eglanteriae*, ♀, The Netherlands: 1 — habitus, lateral view; 2 — metasoma, lateral view; 3 — antenna; 4 — aphid mummy (photographs: Frederique Bakker).

Figs 5–11. *Aphidius eglanteriae*, France: 5 — ♀, habitus, lateral view; 6 — ♂, habitus, lateral view; 7 — ♀, head; 8 — ♀, metasoma, lateral view; 9 — ♀, propodeum; 10 — ♀, first metasomal tergite, dorsal view; 11 — ♀, first metasomal tergite, lateral view.

pterostigma 4.5 times longer than its maximum width and 1.2 times as long as metacarpus.

Male: 15 (16)-segmented antenna, this is less than reported in literature: 17- according to Starý (1973) and 18–19- according to Das & Chakrabarti (1990). It seems that males have also a lower number of costulae on anterolateral area of the first metasomal tergite than females.

Number of antennal segments and costulae on anterolateral area of the first metasomal tergite could be variable characters and probably depend on specimen size.

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